

Interval Reduced Order Surrogate Modelling Framework for Uncertainty Quantification

Ghifari Adam Faza^{a,*}, Keivan Shariatmadar^a, Hans Hallez^b, David Moens^c

^a*KU Leuven, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Division LMSD, Campus Bruges, Belgium*

^b*KU Leuven, Department of Computer science, Division DistriNet, Campus Bruges, Belgium*

^c*KU Leuven, Department of Mechanical engineering, Division LMSD, Campus De Nayer, St.-Katelijne-Waver, Belgium*

Abstract

Surrogate models are widely used in the engineering community to approximate costly and large evaluation processes, such as difficult experiments or expensive simulations. This paper presents a non-intrusive framework for epistemic surrogate modelling, which is based on proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) and polynomial chaos expansion (PCE) for interval observations. In physical systems modelling, it is important to consider both aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty by constructing an uncertainty model to be included in the surrogate model. However, existing frameworks have a major limitation in that they can only handle scalar data observations and are not designed for non-deterministic observations like interval data. In many applications, the observed data can be inherently non-scalar due to various factors, such as observation uncertainties, conflicting data, or summarized data. In our proposed framework, we integrate POD for interval data with PCE for interval observations. Firstly, we employ interval POD to obtain an optimally reduced-order basis from the full-order snapshot. Then, we approximate this reduced-order basis using a non-intrusive interval PCE method. Allowing non-scalar data, such as intervals, is advantageous as it takes into account more information in the physical system modelling.

Keywords: Uncertainty Quantification, Surrogate Model, Reduced Order Model, Interval Analysis

*Corresponding author

1. Introduction

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is the process of quantifying uncertainties in the observed variables of a system in its inputs and responses. It has been widely applied in scientific and engineering fields, including fluid mechanics [1, 2] and structural mechanics [3, 4]. UQ offers a range of methodologies and techniques to effectively address uncertainty, enabling tasks such as reliability analysis and robust optimisation. UQ also encompasses global sensitivity analysis (GSA), which aims to quantify the contribution of each input variable and their interactions with the system output [5].

Figure 1: Illustration of epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty.

Depending on the nature of the uncertainty, the types of uncertainty are categorized into two groups which are often referred to as *aleatoric (statistical)* and *epistemic (systematic)* uncertainty [6, 7, 8]. The aleatoric component of uncertainty refers to the inherent randomness that naturally exists in a system. This type of uncertainty is irreducible, meaning that the stochastic component cannot be reduced by additional sources of information. Consequently, even the best predictor cannot accurately predict the outcome of the system based on certain input variables. Instead, the predictor provides a statistical measure which represents possible outcomes. A common example of aleatoric uncertainty is dice rolling. The stochastic component of dice rolling cannot be reduced with any additional information. Instead, a model predicts the probability of a specific number appearing. For an ideal 6-sided dice, the probability is $\frac{1}{6}$ for each side. In engineering problems, aleatoric uncertainty can arise from random processes such as ambient conditions.

24 As aleatoric uncertainty is probabilistic, it can be effectively described using
25 well-established probabilistic theories from both frequentist and Bayesian
26 perspectives. Several frameworks [9, 10, 11] have been developed to quantify
27 the uncertainty in this type of problem.

28 Epistemic uncertainty refers to the uncertainty that arises from assumptions
29 or the lack of knowledge or information about the system being investigated.
30 Unlike aleatoric uncertainty, epistemic uncertainty is reducible, meaning that
31 any additional knowledge or information can help reduce the uncertainty in the
32 system. As shown in Figure 1, epistemic uncertainty is depicted by the lack of
33 information present in the data. Hüllermeier and Waegeman [12] provide an
34 example of epistemic uncertainty in the context of the meaning of a word in an
35 unknown language. When given two options, such as "head" or "tail", the
36 probability of each possible answer is equivalent to that of a coin-flipping
37 problem. However, it is important to note that the nature of the problem is
38 different. In the language problem, as we acquire knowledge about the unknown
39 language, the uncertainty decreases. Another example of epistemic uncertainty
40 can be observed in engineering problems, such as determining the load applied
41 to a bridge structure, which can vary based on the vehicles crossing the bridge.
42 Although some argue that load distribution can be measured and estimated through
43 observation, it is crucial to recognize that such measurements can be costly to
44 perform. Additionally, other factors like thermal and wind loads are often
45 assumed, further emphasizing the significance of modelling epistemic uncertainty.
46 It is worth noting that, unlike aleatoric uncertainty, epistemic uncertainty
47 could be non-probabilistic. In literature several approaches are described to
48 model epistemic uncertainty, such as interval [13, 14, 15], fuzzy sets [16, 15],
49 or probability box [17, 18] models are used.

51 An interval model is a fundamental approach for modelling epistemic
52 uncertainty. It does not require the use of probabilistic distributions or more
53 complex representations. Although the interval model is not as informative
54 as the other models such as the contamination model, credal sets, or probability
55 boxes, this straightforward strategy provides advantages by enhancing the
56 interpretability of interval data, which is beneficial for real-world applications.
57 Based on our subjective experience, engineers often assume interval values for
58 certain variables, making interval modelling a convenient choice. Despite its
59 various benefits, the development of interval models for recent machine learning
60 methods is still relatively limited compared to the development of other
61 probabilistic techniques, such as Bayesian methods. The

62 exact reasons behind this trend remain unclear, but one possible factor is
63 the assumption that all observations are scalar-valued, which simplifies the
64 interpretability of the results.

65 In this paper, we propose a formulation for a non-intrusive surrogate
66 modelling framework to handle epistemic uncertainty using interval-based
67 techniques, specifically the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [19]
68 and Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) [20]. The main objective of this
69 abstract is to demonstrate how intervals are incorporated within the POD-
70 PCE framework to represent and analyze epistemic uncertainty. To achieve
71 this objective, we utilize the Interval Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)
72 [21] as the basis for POD, enabling the decomposition of interval-valued
73 matrices. Specifically, we propose an approach to address the challenges
74 associated with the interaction between interval POD and interval PCE,
75 which arise due to the presence of interval-valued intermediate variables.

76 Interval Singular Value Decomposition (ISVD) was initially introduced
77 by Li et al. [21] as a method to address the SVD problem for interval-valued
78 observations. The authors showcased the effectiveness of Interval SVD in
79 an image analysis task using a dataset consisting of images of individuals
80 captured from various angles. Their findings indicated that Interval SVD
81 outperformed classical SVD by incorporating additional information in the
82 form of intervals. Since Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is essen-
83 tially an SVD, we propose the adoption of Interval SVD for Interval POD,
84 leveraging its capabilities to handle interval-valued data. Thus, in this paper,
85 we use the term interval SVD and interval POD interchangeably.

86 Polynomial chaos expansion (PCE) [22, 20, 23, 24] is a widely-known al-
87 gorithm and it has been proven as an efficient way to approximate a physical
88 system in a UQ analysis. Among the other surrogate modeling such as Krig-
89 ing/Gaussian Process Regression [25], PCE has one advantage various quan-
90 tities of interest for uncertainty analysis can be computed analytically [24].
91 Not many research papers have discussed this topic in particular. However,
92 as in general the PCE routines have a lot of similarities with linear regres-
93 sion methods, we can adapt the concept of regression with interval variables
94 [26, 27]. A paper by Wang et al. [28] is one of the few who discussed the
95 interval PCE method. They noted that method such as the conventional
96 interval arithmetic and Taylor series method [29, 30] suffers from an intrin-
97 sic wrapping effect which leads to consistently overestimating the interval
98 uncertainty propagation effect on the system output.

99 In this paper, we explore the utilization of the interval POD-PCE frame-

100 work on two physical problems with interval observation. Scalar POD has
 101 been previously used together with scalar PCE [31, 32]. However, the in-
 102 tegration of both methods under interval data poses challenges such as a
 103 misaligned latent vector in the SVD that is caused by interval-valued latent
 104 space, which is solved through an alignment algorithm proposed by Li et al.
 105 [21] and the problem in handling interval-valued input parameters which is
 106 solved by using two regression models.

107 This paper is structured as follows: Section 3 briefly explains the con-
 108 cept of interval uncertainty and interval proper orthogonal decomposition;
 109 Interval polynomial chaos expansion and the framework integration is ex-
 110 plained in Section 4; the experiments and results are discussed in Section
 111 5; finally, section 6 concludes this paper and points out the potential future
 112 development in the context of epistemic uncertainty and machine learning
 113 for physical systems.

114 **2. Interval Uncertainty and Interval Proper Orthogonal Decompo-** 115 **sition**

116 *2.1. Interval Model*

117 Epistemic uncertainty refers to uncertainty due to the lack of informa-
 118 tion or ignorance. The simplest approach that is used to model epistemic
 119 uncertainty is arguably the interval model, which uses a nonempty subset of
 120 the possible parameter values. An interval of an arbitrary variable or matrix
 121 a_{\dagger} is a pair of the minimum or lower value and the maximum or the upper
 122 value, defined as

$$a_{\dagger} = [\underline{a}, \bar{a}], \underline{a} \leq \bar{a}, \quad (1)$$

123 where \underline{a} is the minimum value or the lower bound and \bar{a} is the maximum
 124 value or the upper bound. A scalar is represented with an interval by setting
 125 $\underline{a} = \bar{a}$. As the interval model is non-probabilistic, no probabilistic information
 126 is required and assumed except we know that $P(a_{\dagger}) = 1$.

127 In a geometrical perspective, a scalar value is represented by a point in
 128 n -dimensional space, for example in 2-dimensional space a scalar value is
 129 represented by a point with coordinate (x, y) . In contrast, an interval is
 130 represented by a hypercube (n -dimensional analogue of rectangle $n = 2$ or
 131 cube $n = 3$) in \mathbb{R}^n . For example, in 2-dimensional space, interval values are
 132 a rectangle as shown in Figure 2.

133 As the interval representation is not scalar, thus the algebraic operations
 134 are different. Given two intervals a_{\dagger} and b_{\dagger} some of the basic interval algebraic
 135 operations [33] are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \textit{Addition} : [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] + [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] = [\underline{a} + \underline{a}, \bar{a} + \bar{a}] \\
 & \textit{Subtraction} : [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] - [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] = [\underline{a} - \bar{a}, \bar{a} - \underline{a}] \\
 & \textit{Multiplication} : [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] \times [\underline{a}, \bar{a}] = \tag{2} \\
 & \quad [\min(\underline{a} \times \underline{a}, \underline{a} \times \bar{a}, \bar{a} \times \underline{a}, \bar{a} \times \bar{a}), \\
 & \quad \max(\underline{a} \times \underline{a}, \underline{a} \times \bar{a}, \bar{a} \times \underline{a}, \bar{a} \times \bar{a})].
 \end{aligned}$$

136 If one or both of the intervals collapse into a scalar, we directly substitute the
 137 interval representation $[\underline{a}, \bar{a}]$ with $[a, a]$. These definitions are the building
 138 blocks for the mathematical operations throughout the whole paper. For
 more detailed and complex operations, the reader can refer to [33, 34].

Figure 2: Illustration of interval data in 2-dimensional space.

139

140 2.2. Interval Proper Orthogonal Decomposition

141 Proper orthogonal decomposition (POD), also well-known as Karhunen-
 142 Loéve decomposition [35, 36, 37] has been used widely in engineering analysis
 143 to obtain the approximation of lower dimension representation of turbulent
 144 flows [38], structural analysis [39], and dynamical system [19]. The POD
 145 requires a $N \times m$ snapshot matrix A which is typically arranged in such a
 146 way, that for example, in the transient 2D fluid flow turbulent simulation
 147 N is the number of probe or mesh element and m is the number of the
 148 time step. The snapshot matrix is then decomposed through a lower-rank
 149 approximation using a singular value decomposition (SVD):

$$A \approx U \Sigma_k V^T, \tag{3}$$

150 where U is an $N \times k$ orthogonal matrix, V is an $m \times k$ orthogonal matrix, and
 151 Σ_k is a $k \times k$ matrix with all elements zero except its diagonal. The diagonal
 152 of Σ_k consists of the singular values of A which are arranged in decreasing
 153 order such that $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_k$. The number of rank approximation k is
 154 either user-defined or obtained by:

$$\frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sigma_i}{\sum_{i=1}^r \sigma_i} \geq \epsilon, \quad k \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \quad (4)$$

$$r = \min(N, m),$$

155 where typically, the value of ϵ is set to be 0.99. The equation 3 provides us
 156 with the optimal approximation of a rank k matrix, as it is the closest to the
 157 original matrix A in terms of L_2 Frobenius norm.

158 In a conventional Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) procedure,
 159 a snapshot matrix A is constructed with dimensions of $N \times m$, where N
 160 represents the number of observed values in a field (e.g., the number of el-
 161 ements in a mesh) and m signifies the number of input/physical parameter
 162 combinations (i.e., the number of samples). This matrix is then decomposed
 163 into the product of three matrices, $A = U\Sigma V^T$, where U is a unitary matrix,
 164 Σ is a diagonal matrix of singular values, and V^T denotes the transpose of a
 165 matrix V . By defining B as ΣV^T , we obtain:

$$A = UB. \quad (5)$$

166 An important property of this formulation is that the matrix U possesses the
 167 unitary property, which allows us to compute B as $B = U^T A$.

168 Given an interval matrix $A_{\dagger} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ where each element $A_{\dagger ij}$ in the
 169 matrix is comprised of real-valued intervals $[\underline{a}_{ij}, \bar{a}_{ij}]$, the interval SVD aims
 170 to decompose matrix A_{\dagger} into $A_{\dagger} = U_{\dagger} \Sigma_{\dagger} V_{\dagger}^T$ where each matrix is potentially
 171 interval-valued. Li et al. [21] presented several strategies to handle the
 172 interval-valued matrix. They showed that averaging each component of an
 173 interval matrix A_{\dagger} is be considered the most naive method as it collapses all
 174 of the interval information into scalar-valued data:

$$A_{\dagger avg}[i, j] = \frac{\underline{a}_{ij} + \bar{a}_{ij}}{2}, \quad (6)$$

$$SVD_{avg}(A_{\dagger}) = SVD(A_{\dagger avg}) = U_{avg} \Sigma_{avg} V_{avg}^T.$$

175 An independent decomposition of each lower and upper component of in-
 176 terval matrix A_{\dagger} is considered the first alternative method to perform interval

177 SVD. This is achieved by separating our initial matrix A_{\dagger} into its minimum
 178 and maximum matrices \underline{a} and \bar{a} . Given these entries, we then perform two
 179 separate matrix decompositions:

$$\begin{aligned} SVD(\underline{A}) &= \underline{U}\underline{\Sigma}V^T, \\ SVD(\bar{A}) &= \bar{U}\bar{\Sigma}V^T. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

180 However, the information from the lower and upper matrices should not be
 181 processed independently. Such an independent decomposition strategy leads
 182 to a problem where an error might be introduced to the overall decomposition
 183 [21]. To overcome the problem, we first introduce an $N \times N$ square matrix
 184 $M_{\dagger} = [\underline{M}, \bar{M}] = A_{\dagger}^T \cdot A_{\dagger}$ which is then used to compute the interval singular
 185 value matrix Σ_{\dagger} and interval matrix of latent vectors $U_{\dagger} = [\underline{U}, \bar{U}]$ through an
 186 eigen decomposition:

$$\begin{aligned} eig(\underline{M}) &= \underline{U}\underline{\Sigma}^2, \\ eig(\bar{M}) &= \bar{U}\bar{\Sigma}^2. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

187 As mentioned by the original paper [21], the columns of interval latent
 188 semantics matrix U_{\dagger} are quasi-orthogonal (i.e., we can not treat the constraint
 189 $U_{\dagger}U_{\dagger}^T = I$ as a hard constraint). As an implication, the latent vectors might
 190 be misaligned. To approximate the quasi-orthonormality, Li et al. [21] proved
 191 that the only way to do this is by achieving $\underline{U}_{[:,i]} \simeq \bar{U}_{[:,i]}$ which can be seen
 192 as an alignment problem. To solve this problem, Li et al. [21] proposed an
 193 interval-valued latent semantic alignment (ILSA) algorithm, which will not
 194 be discussed in this paper. The aligned interval U_{\dagger} and also the adjusted Σ_{\dagger}
 195 are then written as U_{\dagger}^* and Σ_{\dagger}^* respectively. These aligned variables are then
 196 used to compute the interval-valued \tilde{V}_{\dagger} matrix:

$$\tilde{V}_{\dagger}^T = (\Sigma_{\dagger}^*)^{-1} \cdot (U_{\dagger}^*)^{-1} \cdot A_{\dagger}. \tag{9}$$

197 Later, the interval-valued V_{\dagger} matrix will be used to recompute matrix \tilde{U}_{\dagger} :

$$\tilde{U}_{\dagger} = A_{\dagger} \cdot (\tilde{V}_{\dagger}^T)^{-1} \cdot (\Sigma_{\dagger}^*)^{-1} \tag{10}$$

198 Finally, through all of these steps, we obtain:

$$\tilde{A}_{\dagger} = \tilde{U}_{\dagger}\Sigma_{\dagger}^*\tilde{V}_{\dagger}^T \tag{11}$$

199 **3. Interval Polynomial Chaos Expansion and Framework Integra-**
 200 **tion**

201 In any given system, let $\Theta = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m]$ represent a matrix of physi-
 202 cal design parameters variations (such as geometry, temperature, and time),
 203 and let $\mathbf{Y} = [\mathbf{y}_1, \mathbf{y}_2, \dots, \mathbf{y}_m]$ represent the corresponding output matrix of
 204 the variable of interest. The objective of surrogate modelling is to approxi-
 205 mate the relationship between the physical parameter θ and its corresponding
 206 output \mathbf{y} using a mathematical model. In the context of using POD-PCE as
 207 a surrogate model, POD is mainly used to construct a lower-rank represen-
 208 tation of the physical system. Where this can be achieved by decomposing
 209 output matrix \mathbf{Y} into two rank- k matrices as shown in equation 5:

$$\mathbf{Y} = UB, \quad (12)$$

210 where $U \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times k}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times m}$. If we consider a simple 2D fluid flow
 211 as an example, the size of matrix \mathbf{Y} is $N \times m$, where N is the number
 212 of the discretization element (mesh), and m is the number of physical pa-
 213 rameter variations. Correspondingly, rank- k matrix U represent the spatial
 214 component and matrix B represents the physical parameters, where k can
 215 be determined by the user or via equation 4. Furthermore, each column of
 216 matrix B , denotes a vector that corresponds to a physical parameter θ . This
 217 vector, denoted by b is often called the POD coefficient.

218 Now, given any unseen value of physical parameter θ^* , we estimate the
 219 value of \tilde{b} . Such that, we are able to estimate the new system output $\tilde{\mathbf{y}}$.
 220 Technically, estimating the value of \tilde{b} given θ^* can be done by any regression
 221 method. However in this paper, we arbitrarily choose the PCE regression
 222 model. The PCE regression is defined as:

$$B = \sum_{\alpha \in \mathbb{N}^d} c_\alpha \phi_\alpha(\Theta), \quad (13)$$

223 where $\phi_\alpha(\Theta)$ corresponds to multivariate orthonormal polynomials such as
 224 Legendre polynomials, element α_i defined in multi-index $\alpha \in \mathbb{N}^d$ indicates
 225 the degree of ϕ_α , and c_α represents the coefficient of the PCE regression.

226 To avoid the high computational effort in equation (13) due to the summa-
 227 tion over the whole domain, we replace the infinite summation in an infinite
 228 domain with a finite-term summation:

$$B \approx \tilde{B} := \sum_{\alpha=0}^S c_\alpha \phi_\alpha(\Theta), \quad (14)$$

229 where the number of expansion terms $S + 1$ is a function of the dimensions
 230 (d) of \mathbf{X} and the highest order (p) of the polynomials $\phi(X)$ [23], defined as:

$$S := \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{1}{j!} \prod_{r=0}^{j-1} (d+r) = \frac{(d+p)!}{d!p!}. \quad (15)$$

231 Given a set of pairs between physical parameter Θ and the corresponding
 232 POD coefficient \mathbf{B} , we set the physical parameter as the independent variable
 233 and POD coefficient as the dependent variable for the PCE regression. To
 234 determine the PCE coefficients c_α , a least-squares minimization problem is
 235 employed:

$$\mathbf{c} := \operatorname{argmin} \sum_{j=1}^m \left(B^{(j)} - \sum_{\alpha=0}^S c_\alpha \phi_\alpha(\Theta^{(j)}) \right)^2. \quad (16)$$

Figure 3: Interval POD-PCE framework workflow.

236 Given an interval-valued system parameter matrix Θ_t and its correspond-
 237 ing responses \mathbf{Y}_t , we are no longer able to use the standard approach of the

238 SVD, instead we use the interval SVD method. The interval SVD matrices,
 239 given by $\mathbf{Y}_\dagger = \tilde{U}_\dagger \Sigma_\dagger^* \tilde{V}_\dagger$, has 3 alternative forms to be presented as suggested
 240 by Li et al. [21]. First, we present it as interval-valued factor matrices
 241 $\tilde{U}_\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times k}$, $\tilde{V}_\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times k}$ and interval-valued singular matrix $\Sigma_\dagger^* \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$ as
 242 presented in eq. 11.

243 Second, we present average-valued factor matrices $U_{avg} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times k}$, $V_{avg} \in$
 244 $\mathbb{R}^{m \times k}$ and interval-valued singular matrix $\Sigma_\dagger \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times k}$:

$$U_{avg} = \frac{\tilde{U} + \bar{U}}{2}, \quad V_{avg} = \frac{\tilde{V} + \bar{V}}{2}, \quad (17)$$

245 where \tilde{U} , \bar{U} , \tilde{V} , \bar{V} are the components of \tilde{U}_\dagger and \tilde{V}_\dagger as shown in equation 9
 246 and 10 respectively. Variable U_{avg} and V_{avg} are later normalized in L_2 -norm,
 247 while $\underline{\Sigma}^*$ and $\bar{\Sigma}^*$ need to be updated accordingly. Hence, the result is:

$$\mathbf{Y}_\dagger = U_{avg} \Sigma_\dagger^* V_{avg}^T. \quad (18)$$

248 Third, we average all of the matrices, and the formula for averaging U_\dagger and
 249 V_\dagger is given in eq. 17. In the same manner, we take the average of the
 250 singular matrix Σ_\dagger , resulting in $A_{avg} = U_{avg} \Sigma_{avg} V_{avg}^T$. However, the latter
 251 representation eliminates the ability to restore the original interval matrix
 252 A_\dagger .

253 According to Li et al. [21] the second interval SVD representation which
 254 is shown in equation 18 gives the best matrix reconstruction performance
 255 compared to the original representation in equation 11. Further, we modify
 256 equation 18, thus it has similar structures with equation 12. There are two
 257 ways to modify the equations:

$$\mathbf{Y}_\dagger := L_\dagger V_{avg}^T, \quad \text{and} \quad (19)$$

258

$$\mathbf{Y}_\dagger := U_{avg} B_\dagger, \quad (20)$$

259 where $L_\dagger := U_{avg} \Sigma_\dagger^*$ and $B_\dagger := \Sigma_\dagger^* V_{avg}^T$.

260 These two equations are now structurally similar with equation 12. In
 261 the same manner, we define V_{avg}^T as the interval POD coefficients for equation
 262 19 and B_\dagger as the interval POD coefficients for equation 20. Then, we train
 263 PCE regression models to approximate the relation between the interval-
 264 valued physical parameters Θ_\dagger with the corresponding POD coefficients for
 265 each alternative POD coefficients V_{avg}^T and B_\dagger . However, the standard PCE

266 regression could not handle interval-valued input and output. Therefore, to
 267 handle the interval-valued variables, we use two methods in this work. In the
 268 first method, similar to [26] we take the averaged value of the interval input
 269 and output to obtain the PCE coefficient c_α through a standard least square
 270 procedure, written as:

$$\min_{c_{\alpha_\mu}} \|V_{avg}^T - c_{\alpha_\mu} \phi_\alpha(\Theta_\mu)\|^2, \quad (21)$$

271 where $\Theta_\mu = (\underline{\Theta} + \overline{\Theta})/2$. This representation is suitable for the averaged-value
 272 PCE as our POD coefficient (V_{avg}) is a scalar value. Meanwhile, the latent
 273 vector (L_\dagger) is interval-valued. However, this approach limits the capability
 274 of the method to propagate the interval range information properly from the
 275 input variables as the input variables are simplified into the average value.

276 In the second method, we are using the constrained center and range
 277 method (CCRM) [27]. This method comprises two different regressions: in-
 278 terval center and interval range. The interval center regression is done by
 279 using equation 21 to find the PCE coefficient. Meanwhile, the interval range
 280 regression requires the result to always be positive. Thus, the optimisation
 281 procedure should be constrained:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{c_{\alpha_r}} \|B_r - c_{\alpha_r} \phi_\alpha(\Theta_r)\|^2, \\ \text{s.t. } c_{\alpha_r} \geq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

282 where $\Theta_r = \overline{\Theta} - \underline{\Theta}$ and $B_r = \overline{B} - \underline{B}$. This formulation suits the CCRM PCE
 283 (equation 22) where the POD coefficient is interval-valued. Compared to the
 284 averaged method, this method can propagate the interval range information
 285 from the input variables. However, this method is twice as complex as the
 286 averaged PCE as it requires running the regression twice. The overall work-
 287 flow of the proposed framework, excluding the interval data construction, is
 288 shown in Figure 3.

289 4. Numerical Experiments on Test Problems

290 To demonstrate the effectiveness of the two proposed PCE methods, we
 291 perform experiments on three test cases: a simple bridge truss structure,
 292 2-variables heat conduction, and 2-variables heat conduction with changing
 293 boundary conditions. Additionally, we provide two different settings: homo-
 294 geneous and heterogeneous. In the heterogeneous setting, each sample in the

295 input variable has a unique interval range. Conversely, in the homogeneous
 296 setting, the interval range for each sample remains the same. Mainly, the goal
 297 of these two settings is to see the generalization capability of the proposed
 298 methods.

299 4.1. Bridge Truss Structure

300 First, we consider a simple linear problem to validate the proposed meth-
 301 ods. The bridge-truss structure problem, as illustrated in Figure 4, is adopted
 302 from Blatman and Sudret [40]. The original problem has 10 independent
 303 random variables $\boldsymbol{\xi} = [E_1, E_2, A_1, A_2, P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6]^T$, where A_1 and
 304 E_1 are the cross-sectional area and the modulus of elasticity of the horizontal
 305 bar respectively. Meanwhile, A_2 and E_2 are the cross-sectional areas and
 306 the modulus of elasticity of the diagonal bar respectively. Each force acting
 307 on the bridge is represented by P_1, P_2, \dots, P_6 .

Figure 4: The sketch of bridge truss structure problem.

308 4.1.1. 2-Variables Bridge Truss

309 To validate the proposed method, we simplify the problem into a 2-
 310 dimensional problem. We compare the results obtained from Interval POD-
 311 PCE with those from the scanning method (SM) [28], also known as exhaus-
 312 tive search. The scanning method, historically one of the earliest approaches
 313 to interval analysis, was developed to address the dependency problem that
 314 often leads to excessive conservatism in interval arithmetic. It involves gen-
 315 erating samples within all intervals at the input side and performing deter-
 316 ministic propagation sample by sample. This method can be viewed as a
 317 "Monte Carlo" approach within the intervals. Finally, the extreme values are
 318 extracted from the output to determine the interval bounds after propaga-
 319 tion. To convert the problem into an interval-valued 2-dimensional problem,
 320 we define 2 interval variables P and E where $P = P_1 = P_2 = \dots = P_6$ and
 321 $E_1 = E_2$. The design space of the 2D bridge structure is given in table 1.
 322 Other variables in the problem are held constant where $A_1 = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}m^2$
 323 and $A_2 = 1 \times 10^{-3}m^2$.

Table 1: Design space for 2-variables bridge truss problem.

Variable	Units	Min	Max
E_1, E_2	Pa	1.6×10^{11}	2.2×10^{11}
P	N	3.0×10^4	7.0×10^4

324 To simulate the homogeneous and heterogeneous interval variable set-
 325 ting, first, we perform a random sampling using the Sobol sampling method
 326 throughout the whole design space. Then, we define the interval range for
 327 each sample to be 5% of the design space range for the homogeneous case,
 328 and for the heterogeneous case, we randomize the interval range for each
 329 sample to be 2% - 8% of the design space interval.

Figure 5: Bridge deflection average POD coefficients.

330 A simple linear structural problem implies that the problem is reducible
 331 to a single POD mode as seen in figure 5, which is suitable as a validation
 332 case. In this case, we achieve the maximum RMSE around 0.0007, as shown
 333 in Figure 6. This value can be roughly interpreted as the maximum average
 334 difference between the predicted and reference values, which is approximately
 335 0.7 mm . This difference is relatively small compared to the range of deflection
 336 values, which spans from 1 cm to 5 cm . The advantages of using CCRM can
 337 also be observed in Figure 6 where the RMSE of the CCRM method on the
 338 heterogeneous case is lower than the averaged method.

Figure 6: Root mean squared error for the bridge deflection problem. Averaged POD-PCE (left) and CCRM POD-PCE (right)

339 4.2. 2D Heat Conduction

340 The original problem of the stationary 2-dimensional heat conduction is
 341 taken from Konakli and Sudret’s work [41]. The problem is defined within
 342 domain $D = (-0.5, 0.5) \times (-0.5, 0.5)$ as shown in Figure 7. It defines a heat
 343 source generated within area A which is a square domain with dimension
 344 $A = (0.2, 0.3)m \times (0.2, 0.3)m$. By default, the value of the heat source
 345 $Q = 2 \cdot 10^3 W/m^3$. As the problem is originally designed for reliability analysis
 346 benchmark, the output of interest is the average temperature over area B
 347 where $B = (-0.3, -0.2)m \times (-0.3, -0.2)m$. However, we might modify the
 348 output of interest to be the temperature distribution over the whole domain
 to demonstrate the capability of the framework.

Figure 7: Problem domain and boundary condition.

349

350 The temperature field $T(\mathbf{z}), \mathbf{z} \in D$ is governed by a partial differential
 351 equation as follows:

$$-\nabla(\kappa(\mathbf{z})\nabla T(\mathbf{z})) = QI_A(\mathbf{z}). \quad (23)$$

352 The boundary condition is set to be constant temperature $T = 0$ at the top
 353 of the domain, and the Neumann boundary condition is applied on the left,
 354 right, and bottom of the domain. Matrix I_A is an indicator function which
 355 equals 1 if $\mathbf{z} \in A$ and 0 otherwise. Variable $\kappa(\mathbf{z})$ denotes the conduction
 356 coefficient across the domain, which can be set as a constant or as a lognormal
 357 random field as defined in the original formulation of the problem [41]. In
 358 our test case, we treat the conduction coefficient to be constant across the
 359 plate.

360 4.2.1. 2-Variables Heat Conduction

361 Similar to the bridge truss problem, here we present a 2 variables problem
 362 to demonstrate the validity of the present method. The result from interval
 363 POD-PCE will be compared with the scanning method (SM) [28]. In this
 364 problem, we define the heat conduction coefficient across the domain as a
 365 constant within the design space of $[\underline{\kappa}, \bar{\kappa}] = [3, 5]W/^\circ C m$. We also define
 366 the heat generated over an area A to be within the design space with range
 367 $[\underline{Q}, \bar{Q}] = [2000, 4000]W/m^3$.

368 To construct the interval input variable, we use the same method as the
 369 previous problem. We define the interval range for each sample to be 5%
 370 of the design space range for the homogeneous case and the heterogeneous
 371 case, we randomize the interval range for each sample to be 2% - 8% of the
 372 design space interval. One example of the heat conduction problem solution
 373 is given in the temperature profile in Figure 8a.

Figure 8: (a) 2D heat conduction temperature profile and (b) Temperature distribution cross-section at $y = 0.2$ for one sample from heterogeneous 2D heat problem.

374 The evaluation of the interval POD-PCE in the heat conduction problem
 375 poses a unique challenge since the heat conduction is evaluated using $101 \times$
 376 101 discretization which results in a very large snapshot matrix. Thus, it
 377 requires more computational power. Despite that, the interval POD-PCE
 378 can provide a good approximation of the minimum and maximum value of
 379 the reference temperature distribution interval as shown in figure 8b. This
 380 experiment for 10201 elements, compared to 13 elements in the previous
 381 problem, proves that the interval POD-PCE framework is a general method
 382 that can be applied to many applications.

383 Also similar to the bridge structure deflection problem, the relationship
 384 between the input parameters of the heat source and the plate's heat con-
 385 ductivity appears to have a linear correlation. A similar Proper Orthogonal
 386 Decomposition (POD) coefficients plot (figure 9) can also be observed, where
 387 only the first mode is significant while the others are negligible.

388 In this test case, we also compare both the averaged method and the
 389 CCRM method. The result shows that there is no significant difference be-
 390 tween using CCRM and the averaged method in both homogeneous and
 391 heterogeneous heat conduction cases, quite contrary to the bridge structure
 392 case. It's worth noting that both methods perform very well achieving an
 393 RMSE of 0.02 which can be roughly interpreted as the average difference
 394 between the ground truth and the predicted value is only $0.02^\circ C$ when the
 395 plate temperature ranges from $0^\circ C$ to around $6^\circ C$.

396 Additionally, we also introduce a condition that determines the coverage
 397 of interval-valued variable regression that we call conservativity. The idea

Figure 9: Heat conduction average POD coefficients.

Figure 10: Root mean squared error for the heat conduction problem. Averaged POD-PCE (left) and CCRM POD-PCE (right)

398 behind the conservative condition is that:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{f^*}(x_{\dagger}) &\geq \overline{y}(x_{\dagger}), \\ \underline{f^*}(x_{\dagger}) &\leq \underline{y}(x_{\dagger}). \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

399 Where, $f^*(x_{\dagger})$ and $y(x_{\dagger})$ denote the predicted and the actual interval value
 400 of a given interval input variable x_{\dagger} , respectively. Therefore, by combining
 401 the conservativity condition with a widely recognized measure of regression
 402 performance, such as RMSE, we can establish that a proficient interval pre-
 403 predictor is a model that not only attains high accuracy (low RMSE) but also
 404 upholds the crucial conservativity condition. While preserving this condition

Table 2: Conservativity metric value for 2D heat conduction problem.

		$\underline{\mathcal{C}}$	$\overline{\mathcal{C}}$
Homogeneous	Mean	0.525	0.35
	CCRM	0.375	0.55
Heterogeneous	Mean	0.575	0.225
	CCRM	0.775	0.225

405 may appear trivial at first, we contend that it holds significant importance
 406 in subsequent applications, including optimization and decision-making pro-
 407 cesses, as any mispredictions could potentially have disastrous consequences.

408 To measure the conservativity we introduce the conservativity metric,
 409 that mathematically defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \overline{\mathcal{C}} &= \frac{1}{|X_{\dagger}|} \sum_{x_{\dagger} \in X_{\dagger}} \mathbb{1} \left\{ \overline{f}^*(x_{\dagger}) \geq \overline{y}(x_{\dagger}) \right\}, \\
 \underline{\mathcal{C}} &= \frac{1}{|X_{\dagger}|} \sum_{x_{\dagger} \in X_{\dagger}} \mathbb{1} \left\{ \underline{f}^*(x_{\dagger}) \leq \underline{y}(x_{\dagger}) \right\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{25}$$

410 Where $\mathbb{1}$ denotes the indicator function which value is 1 when the conser-
 411 vativity condition is not violated, and 0 otherwise. The metric we utilize
 412 in this study quantifies the number of data fractions within a given dataset
 413 that does not violate the conservativity condition. Although our proposed
 414 methods exhibit strong prediction accuracy, they still encounter challenges
 415 in maintaining the conservativity condition, as shown in table 2.

416 4.3. Modified Heat Conduction

417 The two previous test cases that were presented may be considered too
 418 simplistic, as the POD coefficient only has one dominant component. Alter-
 419 natively, we can observe that the rank of the snapshot matrix A is 1. This is
 420 primarily attributed to the linear relationship between the input parameters
 421 and the solution. For instance, in the heat conduction problem, modifying
 422 the conductivity coefficient and the heat production rate over area A will
 423 simply result in shifting the temperature surface shown in Figure 8a up or
 424 down. In other cases, such as the bridge truss deflection problem, the magni-
 425 tude of deflection at one node is directly proportional to the deflection at the
 426 other nodes. As a result, the snapshot matrix is not linearly independent.

Figure 11: Modified heat conduction problem.

427 We propose to modify the heat conduction problem by introducing a
 428 new boundary condition that incorporates arbitrary periodic functions, as
 429 illustrated in Figure 11. In this study, the heat source and heat conductivity
 430 values are kept constant at $Q = 2 \cdot 10^3 W/m^3$ and $\kappa = 5W/^\circ Cm$, respectively.
 431 In this problem, we employ two independently distributed variables, ϕ_a and
 432 ϕ_b , as the independent variables within a design space range of $[0, 0.5\pi]$.

433 In contrast to the previous two problems, changing the boundary condi-
 434 tion of the heat conduction problem results in a linearly independent problem.
 435 As shown in Figure 12, the magnitude of the average POD coefficients now
 436 has more than one component, despite the domination of the first compo-
 437 nent. However, as shown in figure 13, increasing the interval POD rank only
 438 slightly changes the overall performance of the model.

Figure 12: Modified heat conduction average POD coefficient.

Figure 13: Interval POD rank effect to modified heat conduction prediction accuracy.

439 The model on the modified problem exhibits a significantly inferior perfor-
 440 mance, as depicted in Figure 14. This observation suggests that the current
 441 method encounters challenges in accurately approximating a relatively com-
 442 plex problem. Additionally, Figure 15b, which displays the cross-section of
 443 the temperature field, reveals that the current method fails to preserve the
 444 conservativity condition of the upper and lower temperature distributions
 445 as suggested in equation 24. Similar to the previous test case, we also pro-
 446 vide the conservativity metric in table 3, which strongly indicates that our
 447 proposed methods do not comply with the conservativity condition. Conse-
 448 quently, in our future research, we aim to address the existing issues in the
 449 current approach.

Table 3: Conservativity metric value for modified heat conduction problem.

		$\underline{\mathcal{C}}$	$\overline{\mathcal{C}}$
Homogeneous	Mean	0	0
	CCRM	1	0
Heterogeneous	Mean	0	0
	CCRM	1	0

Figure 14: Root mean squared error for the modified heat conduction problem. Averaged POD-PCE (left) and CCRM POD-PCE (right)

Figure 15: (a) Modified heat conduction temperature profile and (b) Temperature distribution cross-section at $y = 0.2$ for one sample from heterogeneous interval modified heat problem.

450 5. Conclusions and Future Works

451 In the present paper, we advance a formulation for a non-intrusive frame-
 452 work for epistemic uncertainty that is based on Proper Orthogonal Decom-
 453 position (POD) and Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) regarding interval-
 454 valued data. The core objective of this paper is to demonstrate how epistemic
 455 uncertainty in the form of intervals can be incorporated into the system. To
 456 achieve this objective, we proposed the utilization of the interval Singular
 457 Value Decomposition (SVD) as the foundation of interval POD, allowing the

458 decomposition of the interval-valued matrix which results in equation 18.
459 We then integrate the interval POD formulation with the PCE algorithm to
460 enable the framework to have predictive power given an unknown physical
461 parameter interval. However, the classical PCE algorithm does not natively
462 support the utilization of interval-valued variables. Thus in this paper, we
463 proposed the formulation of the POD coefficient in equation 19 and 20 to
464 overcome this limitation. To enable the PCE algorithm to handle interval-
465 valued variables we tried two approaches, first the averaged-value method
466 which is given in equation 21, and the constrained center and range method
467 (CCRM) given in equation 22.

468 In this study, a comparative analysis was conducted to evaluate the effi-
469 cacy of two methods in addressing two use cases: bridge structure and heat
470 conduction. The investigations were carried out in both homogeneous and
471 heterogeneous settings. Notably, our findings showcase a significant advan-
472 tage in utilizing the CCRM (constrained center and range method) approach
473 when tackling the bridge structure problem. This favourable outcome can
474 be attributed to the innate capability of the CCRM method to effectively
475 propagate interval range information from input variables to the system's
476 output. Conversely, the behavior of the CCRM method in the heat con-
477 duction which didn't result in accuracy improvement domain needs to be
478 further investigated. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that both methodologies
479 exhibited commendable performance levels in both test cases, signifying their
480 remarkable potential and validity.

481 The proposed approach, as demonstrated in the last test case, has certain
482 limitations, particularly in modelling non-linear problems. This limitation re-
483 sults in a performance that is inferior to that of linear problems. Moreover,
484 the current approach fails to ensure the coverage of the temperature field, as
485 depicted in figure 15b. Given the significance of a coverage guarantee in un-
486 certainty quantification, it is important for future studies to incorporate this
487 guarantee into their approach. Moreover, it is essential for the framework to
488 have the capability to handle and incorporate different types of uncertainty
489 sources, including probabilistic and probabilistic-interval cases. Furthermore,
490 in order to validate the method, the intention is to conduct physical exper-
491 iments in the future that encompass epistemic uncertainties in both input
492 parameters and the overall process.

493 **Acknowledgments**

494 This work was supported by granted H2020 FETOPEN-2018-2019-2020-
495 01 European project, *Epistemic AI* under grant agreement No. 964505 (E-
496 pi). The code used for this analysis is provided in a repository at [github.com/fazaghifari/interval-](https://github.com/fazaghifari/interval-surrogate-pod)
497 [surrogate-pod](https://github.com/fazaghifari/interval-surrogate-pod). The authors welcome requests for additional information re-
498 garding the material presented in this paper.

499 **References**

- 500 [1] P. J. Roache, Quantification of uncertainty in computational
501 fluid dynamics, *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics* 29 (1997)
502 123–160. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.29.1.123>.
503 doi:10.1146/annurev.fluid.29.1.123.
- 504 [2] H. N. Najm, Uncertainty quantification and polynomial
505 chaos techniques in computational fluid dynamics, *An-*
506 *ual Review of Fluid Mechanics* 41 (2009) 35–52. URL:
507 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.010908.165248>.
508 doi:10.1146/annurev.fluid.010908.165248.
- 509 [3] A. D. Kiureghian, P. Liu, Structural reliabil-
510 ity under incomplete probability information, *Jour-*
511 *nal of Engineering Mechanics* 112 (1986) 85–104. URL:
512 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0733-9399\(1986\)112:1\(85\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(1986)112:1(85)).
513 doi:10.1061/(ASCE)0733-9399(1986)112:1(85).
- 514 [4] S. Adhikari, M. Friswell, K. Lonkar, A. Sarkar, Experimen-
515 tal case studies for uncertainty quantification in structural dy-
516 namics, *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics* 24 (2009) 473–
517 492. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.probengmech.2009.01.005>.
518 doi:10.1016/j.probengmech.2009.01.005.
- 519 [5] I. Sobol', Global sensitivity indices for nonlinear mathe-
520 matical models and their monte carlo estimates, *Math-*
521 *ematics and Computers in Simulation* 55 (2001) 271–280.
522 URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-4754\(00\)00270-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-4754(00)00270-6).
523 doi:10.1016/s0378-4754(00)00270-6.

- 524 [6] S. C. Hora, Aleatory and epistemic uncertainty in probabil-
525 ity elicitation with an example from hazardous waste manage-
526 ment, *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 54 (1996)
527 217–223. URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0951-8320\(96\)00077-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0951-8320(96)00077-4).
528 doi:10.1016/s0951-8320(96)00077-4.
- 529 [7] A. D. Kiureghian, O. Ditlevsen, Aleatory or epistemic?
530 does it matter?, *Structural Safety* 31 (2009) 105–112.
531 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strusafe.2008.06.020>.
532 doi:10.1016/j.strusafe.2008.06.020.
- 533 [8] K. Shariatmadar, H. Hallez, D. Moens, Identification of imprecision
534 in data using epsilon-contamination advanced uncertainty model, in:
535 *Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*, Springer International Pub-
536 lishing, 2021, pp. 157–172. doi:10.1007/978-3-030-77256-7_14.
- 537 [9] S. Marelli, B. Sudret, Uqlab: A framework for uncer-
538 tainty quantification in matlab, in: *Vulnerability, Uncer-*
539 *tainty, and Risk*, American Society of Civil Engineers, 2014,
540 p. 1. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1061/9780784413609.257>.
541 doi:10.1061/9780784413609.257.
- 542 [10] A. Olivier, D. G. Giovanis, B. Aakash, M. Chauhan, L. Van-
543 danapu, M. D. Shields, Uqpy: A general purpose python
544 package and development environment for uncertainty quan-
545 tification, *Journal of Computational Science* 47 (2020)
546 101204. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2020.101204>.
547 doi:10.1016/j.jocs.2020.101204.
- 548 [11] L. R. Zuhail, G. A. Faza, P. S. Palar, R. P. Liem, Performance assessment
549 of kriging with partial least squares for high-dimensional uncertainty
550 and sensitivity analysis, *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*
551 66 (2023). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00158-023-03547-3>.
552 doi:10.1007/s00158-023-03547-3.
- 553 [12] E. Hullermeier, W. Waegeman, Aleatoric and epistemic
554 uncertainty in machine learning: an introduction to con-
555 cepts and methods, *Machine Learning* 110 (2021) 457–
556 506. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-021-05946-3>.
557 doi:10.1007/s10994-021-05946-3.

- 558 [13] J. M. Keynes, A Treatise on Probability, volume 8 of *The Collected*
559 *Writings of John Maynard Keynes*, Macmillan, London, 1921.
- 560 [14] S. Kuznetsov, Interval Statistical Models, Chapman & Hall/CRC Mono-
561 graphs on Statistics & Applied Probability, CRC Press, Boca Raton,
562 1997.
- 563 [15] K. Shariatmadar, M. Versteyhe, Numerical linear program-
564 ming under non-probabilistic uncertainty models - inter-
565 val and fuzzy sets, International Journal of Uncertainty,
566 Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems 28 (2020) 469–
567 495. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1142/s0218488520500191>.
568 doi:10.1142/s0218488520500191.
- 569 [16] R. E. Bellman, L. A. Zadeh, Decision-making in a fuzzy environment,
570 Management science 17 (1970) 141–164.
- 571 [17] S. Ferson, L. R. Ginzburg, Different methods are
572 needed to propagate ignorance and variability, Relia-
573 bility Engineering and System Safety 54 (1996) 133–144.
574 URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0951-8320\(96\)00071-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0951-8320(96)00071-3).
575 doi:10.1016/s0951-8320(96)00071-3.
- 576 [18] K. Shariatmadar, M. Versteyhe, Linear programming under p-
577 box uncertainty model, in: 2019 7th International Conference
578 on Control, Mechatronics and Automation (ICCMA), IEEE, 2019,
579 p. 1. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/iccma46720.2019.8988632>.
580 doi:10.1109/iccma46720.2019.8988632.
- 581 [19] A. Chatterjee, An introduction to the proper orthogonal
582 decomposition, Current Science 78 (2000) 808–817. URL:
583 <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24103957>.
- 584 [20] R. Ghanem, P. D. Spanos, Polynomial chaos in stochastic finite
585 elements, Journal of Applied Mechanics 57 (1990) 197–202. URL:
586 <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2888303>. doi:10.1115/1.2888303.
- 587 [21] M.-L. Li, F. D. Mauro, K. S. Candan, M. L. Sapino, Ma-
588 trix factorization with interval-valued data, IEEE Transac-
589 tions on Knowledge and Data Engineering 33 (2021) 1644–

- 590 1658. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tkde.2019.2942310>.
591 doi:10.1109/tkde.2019.2942310.
- 592 [22] N. Wiener, The homogeneous chaos, *American Journal of Math-*
593 *ematics* 60 (1938) 897. URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2371268>.
594 doi:10.2307/2371268.
- 595 [23] D. Xiu, G. E. Karniadakis, The wiener–askey polyno-
596 mial chaos for stochastic differential equations, *SIAM*
597 *Journal on Scientific Computing* 24 (2002) 619–644.
598 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1137/s1064827501387826>.
599 doi:10.1137/s1064827501387826.
- 600 [24] B. Sudret, Global sensitivity analysis using polynomial chaos ex-
601 pansion, *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 93 (2008)
602 964–979. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ress.2007.04.002>.
603 doi:10.1016/j.ress.2007.04.002.
- 604 [25] C. Williams, C. Rasmussen, Gaussian processes for regression, in:
605 D. Touretzky, M. Mozer, M. Hasselmo (Eds.), *Advances in Neural In-*
606 *formation Processing Systems*, volume 8, MIT Press, 1995, p. 1.
- 607 [26] L. Billard, E. Diday, Regression analysis for interval-valued data, in:
608 *Studies in Classification, Data Analysis, and Knowledge Organization*,
609 Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2000, pp. 369–374. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-
610 59789-3_58.
- 611 [27] E. de A. Lima Neto, F. de A.T. de Carvalho, Constrained
612 linear regression models for symbolic interval-valued variables,
613 *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis* 54 (2010) 333–
614 347. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2009.08.010>.
615 doi:10.1016/j.csda.2009.08.010.
- 616 [28] L. Wang, Z. Chen, G. Yang, A polynomial chaos ex-
617 pansion approach for nonlinear dynamic systems with in-
618 terval uncertainty, *Nonlinear Dynamics* 101 (2020) 2489–
619 2508. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11071-020-05895-x>.
620 doi:10.1007/s11071-020-05895-x.
- 621 [29] K. Makino, Efficient control of the dependency problem
622 based on taylor model methods, *Reliable Computing* 5 (1999)

- 623 3–12. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1026485406803>.
624 doi:10.1023/a:1026485406803.
- 625 [30] N. Revol, K. Makino, M. Berz, Taylor models and floating-point
626 arithmetic: proof that arithmetic operations are validated in
627 cosy, *The Journal of Logic and Algebraic Programming* 64 (2005)
628 135–154. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlap.2004.07.008>.
629 doi:10.1016/j.jlap.2004.07.008.
- 630 [31] M. Raisee, D. Kumar, C. Lacor, A non-intrusive model reduction ap-
631 proach for polynomial chaos expansion using proper orthogonal decom-
632 position, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineer-*
633 *ing* 103 (2015) 293–312. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.4900>.
634 doi:10.1002/nme.4900.
- 635 [32] X. Sun, X. Pan, J.-I. Choi, Non-intrusive framework of
636 reduced-order modeling based on proper orthogonal de-
637 composition and polynomial chaos expansion, *Journal*
638 *of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 390 (2021)
639 113372. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cam.2020.113372>.
640 doi:10.1016/j.cam.2020.113372.
- 641 [33] T. Sunaga, Theory of interval algebra and its applications to numerical
642 analysis, *RAAG Memoirs, 2-Misc. II* (1958) 547–564.
- 643 [34] G. Alefeld, G. Mayer, Interval analysis: theory and applica-
644 tions, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics* 121 (2000)
645 421–464. URL: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0377-0427\(00\)00342-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0377-0427(00)00342-3).
646 doi:10.1016/s0377-0427(00)00342-3.
- 647 [35] D. D. Kosambi, *Statistics in Function Space*, The Indian Mathematical
648 Society, 1943.
- 649 [36] K. Karhunen, Zur spektraltheorie stochastischer prozesse, *Annales*
650 *Academiae Scientiarum Fennicae. Series A. I. Mathematica* 37 (1947)
651 1–79.
- 652 [37] M. Loève, *Fonctions Aléatoires de Second Ordre (Random Functions of*
653 *Second Order)*, Gauthier-Villars, 1970.

- 654 [38] G. Berkooz, P. Holmes, J. L. Lumley, The proper orthog-
655 onal decomposition in the analysis of turbulent flows, *An-*
656 *ual Review of Fluid Mechanics* 25 (1993) 539–575. URL:
657 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fl.25.010193.002543>.
658 doi:10.1146/annurev.fl.25.010193.002543.
- 659 [39] J. Cusumano, M. Sharkady, B. Kimble, Spatial coherence measurements
660 of a chaotic flexible-beam impact oscillator (1993) aerospace structures:
661 Nonlinear dynamics and system response, American Society of Mechan-
662 ical Engineers, AD-33 (1993) 13–22.
- 663 [40] G. Blatman, B. Sudret, Adaptive sparse polynomial
664 chaos expansion based on least angle regression, *Jour-*
665 *nal of Computational Physics* 230 (2011) 2345–2367.
666 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2010.12.021>.
667 doi:10.1016/j.jcp.2010.12.021.
- 668 [41] K. Konakli, B. Sudret, Reliability analysis of high-
669 dimensional models using low-rank tensor approximations,
670 *Probabilistic Engineering Mechanics* 46 (2016) 18–36. URL:
671 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.probengmech.2016.08.002>.
672 doi:10.1016/j.probengmech.2016.08.002.